

Organizational Cynicism: A Brief Evaluation

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Abstract:

Organizational cynicism is a relatively new concept to be discussed in the area of business administration; while it has a historical background, different dimensions, various reasons and results. Although many employees are experiencing cynicism, they are not aware about the experience, since cynicism is not well-known and well-defined concept in minds. This study is aiming to understand what cynicism is about by drawing a brief evaluation and analysis.

Keywords: Cynicism, Organizational Cynicism, Cynicism Symptoms, Cynical Organizations, Cynic Individuals.

I. Concept and Definition

While the literature on organizational cynicism is rather new, it is seen that there are works on conceptualization, description and scale development on the one hand, and on the other hand there are studies on the premises of organizational cynicism and discovering the results through different contexts and different variables (Tokgöz and Yılmaz, 2008: 291).

According to Dean et al. (1998), organizational cynicism is "a negative attitude involving cognitive, emotional, and behavioral dimensions that a person has developed against the work they are engaged in."

- A belief that the organization lacks honesty,
- A negative feeling towards knitting,
- It is a tendency to show offensive / degrading and critical behavior towards the knight consistent with these beliefs and feelings (Dean, Brandes, and Dahrwadkar, 1998: 345).

Organizational cynicism is a very new subject in the literature of organizational behavior and attracts researchers from different fields such as day-to-day business management, organizational behavior, human resource management, work ethic, public relations from the beginning of the 1990's (Tokgöz and Yılmaz, 2008: 291).

While intense competition, increased creativity and stable developments in organizations continue, the employees of the organization are also affected by these developments. Under these circumstances, employees are beginning to exhibit behaviors they call cynical. Researchers have pointed out that cynicism has increased in business life, increasingly harming organizational competitiveness and the ability to adapt to change, which is today's need (Öncer, 2009: 1).

Cynicism; It is a current of thought which characterizes the individuals as hard-loving, dissatisfied, constantly criticizing the events, enthusiastic and negative thoughts. The main idea of this movement is to leave the second plan for the personal interests of positive personality features such as honesty, justice and sincerity. Cynicism also refers to an attitude and personality characteristic that arises from individual or organizational characteristics, but at the same time it finds difficulty, criticism, and flaw in everything (Eaton, 2000: 7). Cynicism is the reflection of other people's reasoning, honesty and good intentions, and is directly generalized to other matters or situations in terms of credibility (Tan and Tan, 2007: 64).

Cynicism is a general or particular attitude characterized by frustration and frustration with insecurity and negative feelings towards the individual, group, ideology, social communities or institutions (Andersson and Bateman, 1997: 450). In the literature, the concept of cynicism in the workplace is handled in two different ways. The first is dispositional cynicism that arises from the individual's personality and reflects his perspective on life. The other is

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organizational cynicism based on organizational factors that cause cynic attitudes in the individual. Dispositional Cynicism is a decisive personality characteristic in the nature of a person who usually reflects negative perceptions about human behavior (Abraham, 2000: 270). Dispositional cynicism has not been directed to a particular object, but it has been spread to various aspects of the individual's life (Eaton, 2000: 7). Organizational cynicism is a negative attitude which includes the cognitive, emotional and behavioral dimensions that the person has developed for the institute (Dean, Brandes and Dharwadkar, 1998: 345). Accordingly, dispositional cynicism and organizational cynicism are different from each other in structure. That is, while dispositional cynicism originates from the personality of the individual, organizational cynicism originates from the organizational elements that cause cynical attitudes to occur in the individual (Tokgöz and Yılmaz, 2008: 285).

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Cynicism has been dealt with in three perspectives, one in a specific organization, the manager of the firm, and the human nature in general (Andersson and Bateman, 1997: 456). According to Dean's (1995) definition, cynicism is a definite belief that a person has developed against the working organization and management, and management fails to meet their expectations Based on a negative attitude. This cheat is often accompanied by frustration, frustration, and maybe resentment or resignation. What kind of expectations are there from the employers of the employees here? There are many reasons for this. First, employees expect their employers to first care about the goals of the organization and not only to work for their own lives, but also for their well-being. In this case, employees will be cynical when they think that managers are only in their own interests. Second, they expect managers to be able to manage the organization successfully.

In this case, if the employees believe that the management can not succeed, they are still called cynical. Employees also expect the management to manage their employees fairly. In this case, if employees believe that they will be treated unfairly, they are again called cynical. In addition to these, some of the other anticipations that employees may have as a result of cynicism from the administration are that the management has an existing competitive strategy, that the management can take care of the employees in a sincere manner and that the management can provide them with sufficient resources to do their jobs (Dean, 1995).

Cynicism can be defined as a general concept about the success of future organizational changes, including pessimism based on the belief that the leaders of change are clumsy and lazy. In this case, people are trying to make many changes to the organization they are working on, but when they see that very few of these initiatives are successful, they start to show cynical behavior (Wanous, Arnon and Austin, 1994: 269).

In Turkish literature, the concept of 'skepticism' is used instead of the concept of cynicism (Bond and Kirshenbaum, 2004). Although these two concepts are alternatively used in place of each other, they are conceptually separated from each other. While cynicism is described as a decisive personal trait; The skeptic doubts what others have done and said, but can be convinced by showing evidence or giving trial (Tan and Tan, 2007: 67).

II. History of Cynicism

Cynicism is a concept with a history of about 2300 years. For centuries, philosophers, academics, writers, and so on. This concept, which has been discussed by the business world, is an important issue for the business world and organizations today. For this reason it is very important to understand the cynicism and take into account its consequences. Cynicism is an ancient Greek philosophy found almost antecedently by Antisthenes in the fourth century BC, and it is known as cynics of followers of this philosophy primarily related to virtue. The cynics believed that the virtue was the only necessary thing to be happy and that it was fully sufficient to reach happiness.

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Cynicism has emerged as a school of thought and a way of life in ancient Greece. There are various opinions about the place where the concept of cynicism is derived. According to one opinion; It is claimed that the cynical word comes from the Kyön word meaning the Greek dog. In this analogy, cynics were symbolized by dogs in terms of their way of expressing their ideas and exhibiting behaviors in contradiction with tradition. According to another view, the concept of cynicism is claimed to be the name of the place where the cynics, the first place where the teaching of cynics is taught, is located (Kynosarges) (Dean, Brandes and Dharwadkar, 1998: 342).

According to the clan, which does not respect the institutions of the society and expresses these contemptions in terms of both behavior and words, humor was their most frequently used weapon (Tokgöz and Yılmaz, 2008: 285).

The cynics doctrine is based on the Sinopian Diogenes inspired by Alexander the Great's thoughts. Diogenes is famous for its wandering faded light in daylight. When the reason is asked, "I am looking for an honest person" has given the answer. Here, reference is made to the concept of cynicism, which represents the belief that people are not really honest.

The concepts of cynical and cynical cynical and cynicism have taken their place in the sense of what cynicism has taught us (Dean, Brandes and Dharwadkar, 1998: 342). The concept of sincerity is based on the Oxford English dictionary (1985): "Anthistenes, A philosopher of an ancient Greek doctrine that opposes his pleasures. It is a person who teases the sincerity and well-being of human motives and actions. " (Yeni Oxford Resimli Ansiklopedik, 1985).

In recent times, especially in America, public opinion, administrators and politicians are discussing and examining the effects of cynicism. The subject of corporate criminal and administrative misconduct, cynicism, and debates about cynicism have been constantly discussed and debated in the newspapers, magazines and the internet on the subject of cynicism (James, 1995: 15). For example, cartoonist Scott Adams (published in Turkey) 'Ridiculous management' and 'unhappy employees' (Eaton, 2000: 1). In the form of the 'Dilbert Principle' of Scott Adams, which is the continuation of CN Parkinson's 'Parkinson's Law' in 1957 and LJ Peter's 'Peter's Principle' in 1971 He refers to the work in his workplace books in 1996 with a humorous eye (Akin, 2001: 1).

III. Cynicism Symptoms

A few behaviors that may be signs of cynicism are as mentioned below: (www.ecole.org, 2017)

First, when employees think they are unfairly behaving, noble and supreme volunteer behavior in the past is now seen as ridiculous and naïve behaviors. For example, working for very long hours or performing a behavior that is not explicitly stated in the job description for the good of the organization. As a result, workers only work as often as they need to, and they do not do much for more.

Secondly, employees who are cynical will criticize the organization they are most likely to work with in order to remove the pain of their anger and frustration, focusing on the negative elements of the environment. This criticism and detestation will obviously harm the organization if done by the customer. This criticism and detestation, if done against colleagues, will soon lead them to think about the organization in this way. In such a case, cynicism can spread within the organization just like a virus.

Thirdly, employees who are cynical will have insecurities against their practice of implementing significant change programs such as Total Quality or Occupational Participation. Such news will cause employees to believe that managers do not believe in quality principles either because they are looking for ways to improve their careers, or because they think they are in such initiatives to make a good impression as a company.

IV. Reasons for Cynicism

1) Cynical Organizations

There are some several factors that increase cynicism as a whole in organizations:

First, organizations operating in complex and rapidly changing environments are more likely to exhibit cynical attitudes than organizations operating in simple and stable environments. It is much more likely that organizational managers who are engaged in complex environments are making strategic and tactical mistakes and questioning the organizational members' ability of managers in this sense. Managers in organizations operating in such fast-changing environments need to change often in their policies and tactics. Therefore, the uncertainties and mistakes that are experienced will distort the correspondence between the expectation of the employees and what they actually live.

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Another example would be the high rates of cynicism in organizations that have had a high degree of dependence on some groups from outside the organization. Because managers under these circumstances may have to make decisions in the direction of the will of the forces outside the organization, or some powerful groups from outside the organization may cause the formation of cynicism in the organization by forcing them to make their own requests irrespective of agreement with the promises given to the top management.

Another example that can be given in this regard is that if the senior managers in the organization are selected and raised from outside the organization, they are more likely to show more cynicism than the institutions that are selected from the organization. Because such managers who are foreign to such an existing organization culture are not aware of or can not understand the expectations of long-term employees from organizational culture.

2) Cynic Sub Units

What is important here is why some subdivisions or departments of an organization are more cynical than others. There are three things that can cause this:

First, departments that do not play an important role in the organization's success can be more cynical than other departments. Because these departments are recently involved in the decision-making process for financial and technical resources, and they have little influence on top management's decisions.

Secondly, the departments in the leadership of politically weak leaders can be more cynical than other departments. Because these departments will not have too many sources and will not have much impact on decisions.

Third and finally, the departments that are effective and mentioned are categorized at a level above the average compared to other departments. Because the ideas of the people who are mentioned and influenced by the social aspects in these departments are also taken care of by the people around them so that their cynical attitudes can be spread to the whole department.

3) Cynic Individuals

The important thing here is why some individuals are more cynical than others. A few examples of this topic are given below.

First of all, direct experiences can be shown to cause some individuals to be more cynical. For example, employees who think that anticipation will fail to meet by the government may be right in their thinking because they see that these expectations have never met in the past. Here is another interesting question: What happens when an individual who has a cynical attitude about his organization and management transitions to a new job in another organization? Does he take his cynical attitudes with him or does he start all over again with the new administration? This is one of the aspects of your sinsmin needs to be investigated.

Another reason is the possibility of cynicism due to individual differences as a function of personality. The personality factor is related to the attitudes of the individuals about the organization of the organization they are working on, in general terms of their views. According to this, it can be said that generally cynical individuals tend to be cynical about the organization they are working with. Another important point in this regard is shudder; Direct experiences and factors that affect personality. Because naturally, individuals who already have a cynical structure, as well as individuals who do not like it, will have different perceptions of events. For example; Naturally, an individual who already has a cynical structure sees this experience as only bad luck, while an experience as experienced by the individual sees it as evidence of inadequacy and inadequacy.

Finally, it can be mentioned that employees from different cultures or subcultures of different governments may show more cynicism. This is particularly important for many multicultural organizations. There are two reasons why cultural differences can cause cynicism: First, the expectation of the management of individuals from different cultures is also different. The second is the misunderstanding of the expressions of the management of individuals from different cultures.

Concepts Related to Organizational Cynicism

The first concept that can be easily confused with cynicism is "septicism," or the concept of skepticism (Stanley, Meyer, and Topolnytsky, 2005: 436). According to Kanter and Mirvis (1989), septic suspect the reality of the spoken word, but are still eager to be persuaded from the actual point of view. The skeptics doubt the possibility of success, but they are still hopeful that there will be positive developments (Kanter and Mirvis, 1989). According to Reichers et al. (1997), the skeptics are hopeful that there will be positive developments (Reichers, Wanous and Austin, 1997: 48). The cynics, on the other hand, They are less optimistic about success. For this reason, cynicism and septicism seem qualitatively similar in this case, but differ in the degree of optimism about success (Stanley, Meyer and Topolnytsky, 2005: 436).

Another concept that both of the concepts of cynicism and septicism can be confused is the concept of "trust". Along with its interest in organizational change, it is also important recently to think about how this concept differs from cynicism and septicism as well as the growing interest. Although the concept of trust is defined in many different ways up to now, there is still no general definition and measurement method. Although there is no consensus on this issue, many definitions have a common point of "willingness to take risks". That is, one is willing to expose himself to the attack because of the possible negative consequences of others' decisions or actions. It can be seen how the concept of trust contributes to cynicism and septicism if the basic determinants such as honesty, helpfulness and ability are considered. In particular, the concepts of honesty (having a certain principle) and philanthropy (thinking of others' goodness) are related to cynicism negatively and capability (a specific intellectual talent and skill) may be related negatively to septicism. Nevertheless, neither cynicism nor septicism is synonymous with the concept of trust, although they have various common determinants with the concept of trust. Because either cynicism or septicism alone will suffice to create distrust (Stanley, Meyer and Topolnytsky, 2005: 436).

Types of Organizational Cynicism

In recent studies on organizational cynicism, organizational cynicism has been described as a concept that collects the most known types of cynicism in business life (Dean, Brandes and Dharwadkar, 1998: 342). Therefore, it can be said that these concepts are basically not different from one another and possibly overlap to some extent (Öncer, 2009: 3-4). There are five basic types of cynicism in the literature seen.

1) Personality Cynicism

Personality cynicism is the only kind of cynicism as a solid feature found in the nature of a person, which often leads to perceived human behavior as negative. Personality is characterized by cynicism, sarcastic disdain and weak personal relationships, and includes feelings of suspicion and insecurity deeply rooted in people and based on a far-reaching generalization as the world is filled with incompetent, complicit, selfless, selfish and incompetent people who are welcome in social interactions. According to Abraham (2000), personality cynicism is related to one's innate opposition, and he found that personality cynicism, organizational cynicism, is a strong precedent in his work (Abraham, 2000: 270-271).

He also stated that personality cynicism, other forms of cynicism, may also be sources. The reason for this is that the personality cynics tend to look at the negative aspect of life from a negative point of view and therefore they may be more susceptible to adulterated eyebrows. For example, in the absence of such a situation, employee cynicism as seen as being victimized by injustice has been deprived of the full potential of social / institutional cynicism by experiencing more acceptance / disapproval than can be seen by the society And that work cynicism may be the source of organizational change cynicism by perceiving that management is bad despite all the efforts of good intentions (Abraham, 2000: 284).

2) Social / Institutional Cynicism

Social or institutional cynicism can be described as a type of organizational cynicism that arises when people in a country do not trust their state governments and institutions (Kanter and Mirvis, 1989). Another definition is that social cynicism can be seen as a product resulting from violations of the social contract between the individual and society (Abraham, 2000: 271).

The distinctive feature of social cynics is their alienation from the social and economic institutions they accuse of what has happened to them. They take into account the hopelessness of the future, their short-lived interest, and their

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approach and approach to each of their relatives and favors in the form of "What is my deduction?" And these attitudes result in limited interest and sadness towards their work (Kanter and Mirvis, 1989).

3) Employee Cynicism

Employee cynicism generally targets organizations, senior management and other assets in the working environment (Andersson and Bateman, 1997: 450). Employee cynicism is in negative feelings such as disdain, frustration, and hopelessness toward these goals (Dean, Brandes and Dharwadkar, 1998: 344). The cynicism of injustice distinguishes employees from others (Abraham, 2000: 272). Researchers are concerned about working cynicism, psychological contract As a result of their violation (Dean, Brandes and Dharwadkar, 1998: 344). According to the research, it was determined that the working sincerity is related to high level executive fees, low organizational performance and sudden job cuts (Andersson and Bateman, 1997: 463).

4) Organizational Change Cynicism

Cynicism for organizational change is a serious loss of confidence in the leaders who will make the change and a response to attempts to change in the past that have not been fully or clearly successful. This may arise despite the good intentions of the employees responsible for the change, and even the existence of those who think and reasonably judge their goodness and reputation (Reichers, Wanous and Austin, 1994: 48).

The lack of support from the employees in the change work causes the organizations to fail or fail to achieve the desired level of success. Thus, the failure of the genius supports the cynical thought that hinders the desire to try again. However, very few change initiatives have taken place in practice without adequate support from senior management and employees. The success of many innovations depends on a voluntary commitment and the continuation of such behavior. In addition, cynical employees may lose their motivations for job loyalties or jobs, and their absenteeism and complaints may increase. This is an important determinant in the planning and management of change in organizations. For this reason, cynicism is an important obstacle to change in organizations. Reichers et al. (1997) has found a number of recommendations for reducing and managing cynicism on change: (Reichers, Wanous and Austin, 1994: 48-49).

- Include employees in decisions that concern them
- Be aware of the efforts that supervisors have shown in the name of communication and reward
- Informing people about ongoing change studies
- Increase productivity in time
- Make the most of surprise changes
- Increase reliability
- Taking care of the past (accepting mistakes, apologizing, compensating for damages make)

5) Business / Occupation Cynicism

In some professions, stressful interactions with the consumer emotional wear and physically consume employees. For example, in helping professions (nursing, etc.), interaction is problem-oriented, most return is negative, failures are exaggerated, and patients often can not cooperate. Job or occupational cynicism is a sort of coping strategy that prevents someone from making himself competent in business, and causes people to remove themselves from consumers and not see them as individuals. Work is characterized by cynicism, insensitivity, disjointness and impermanence. According to Abraham, work / occupation is related to cynicism, burnout and person-role conflict (Abraham, 2000: 273).

Dimensions of Organizational Cynicism

Organizational cynicism has three sub-dimensions. These dimensions are as described below:

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1) Belief

The first dimension of organizational cynicism is the cognitive dimension which means a belief that the organization lacks honesty. Honesty is defined in the Oxford English Dictionary: integrity in moral rules, integrity, honesty and sincerity about an unspoiled virtuous character, especially in relation to reality and justice. By associating the definition of organizational cynics with this information; Cynicism is defined as sincerity in the motives and actions that motivate the human being and mystery of not believing in the goodness. Thus, organizational cynics believe that their practice of organizing their work shows that they are devoid of principles such as fairness, honesty and sincerity. Cynics can also believe that such principles are frequently sacrificed to personal interests and that unscrupulous behavior is standard. In addition, cynics often believe that there are hidden reasons under their actions. So they expect to face a very trick from sincerity (Dean, Brandes and Dharwadkar, 1998: 346).

2) Affect

The second dimension of organizational cynicism is the affective response dimension, which is a negative feeling toward knitting. Cynicism is not a neutral judgment on the organization and it includes strong emotional reactions. The emotional response dimension is also composed of many emotions. Cynics, for example, can see their organizations as small and feel anger towards their organizations. Cynics may also feel sadness, boredom and even shame when they think of the organization they are working with. Thus, cynicism is associated with various negative emotions. What is curious is that cynics can hear even their hidden pleasures, even when they judge their organization by their own standards, because of their martial supremacy. Thus, it can also be seen that there are not only some beliefs about cynics' organizations, but also some feelings about these beliefs (Dean, Brandes and Dharwadkar, 1998: 346).

3) Behavior

The third and final dimension of organizational cynicism is behavioral attitude, which means a tendency to show degrading / degrading and critical behavior towards the knight. The dimension of behavior, the final dimension of organizational cynicism, expresses a tendency towards negative, and often negative, behaviors. In the old cynics, the most obvious behavioral tendency in terms of cynical behavior is harsh criticism towards knitting. They can be in various forms. The types most clearly expressed are, for example, honesty, sincerity, etc. It is devoid of features. In addition to these, employees often use humor to express cynical attitudes, especially mocking humor. Organizational cynics may be inclined to make pessimistic predictions about future organizational actions. For example, they can predict that a quality initiative will soon be released when it becomes expensive for the organization (Dean, Brandes and Dharwadkar, 1998: 346).

Negative Characteristics of Cynical Employees

It is known that cynical employees in organizations have various characteristics that are formed by negative attitudes and affect processes, operations and even other employees in the organization. Sinic employees are often inclined to underestimate the organization they work with and have a lot of negative thoughts about their organizations, use humiliating expressions, constantly criticize and evil the organizations and managers they work with. Cynical employees are often people who have not been able to achieve their personal visions or who have not been able to reach the organization they desire. These people constantly emphasize that they do not expect anything from the organization they are working on. In addition to these attitudes and behaviors, many negative things that cynical employees have are as follows:

- Emotional burnout
- Carelessness
- self indulgence
- Lack of thought
- Irregularity
- Lack of love

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- Estrangement
- Indifference
- Resignation
- Hopelessness
- Do not trust others
- Doubts
- Humiliation
- Frustration
- Look up from the top
- Low performance
- Interpersonal conflict
- Absenteeism
- Business turnover rate
- Emotional depression

V. Organizational Cynicism Results

Ensuring compliance with the changing conditions of the enterprises allows them to continue their activities with high performance. However, employees with cynical attitudes in the business are obstacles to the change of the business by exhibiting various behaviors such as mistrust of the authority, communication within the organization and misleading instructions and negative criticism to the managers. In other words, working with cynicism negatively affects both the self and the business it operates. It is therefore very important for businesses to recognize and manage this attitude (Tokgöz and Yılmaz, 2008: 284).

There are three important elements in the formation of a sine perspective (Mirvis and Kanter, 1991: 52-53): The first is the existence of high expectations of the general public, or of society, institutions, authorities and futures, which are not true of the individual or of other people and are supported by the media, especially television and advertisers, Praise, and it seems to be an achievement that can be achieved by creating the right image and buying the right products. Secondly, it is a frustration either in person or in other people, and as a result, the feeling of frustration and defeat. The media here also plays an important role in shaping the common spirit. The third is frustration, frustration or suffering, such as thinking and deceiving in a more pessimistic way or being used by others. As a result, cynicism is a way for people to deal with a world that is not friendly, insecure and unstable.

Preface (2009) defines organizational cynicism as a form of illness or irregularity, and both the individual and the organization have adversely affected the working environment by deteriorating the workplace, harming the cultures, reducing internal communication, creating an undesirable, unreliable and stressful atmosphere. He also pointed out that this leads to a decline in the efficiency and efficiency of the organization as a result of its efficient and effective operation.

According to Abraham, when there is insecurity about the integrity of the organization, the cynics will probably not take part in behaviors such as demonstrating prosocial behaviors, advocacy, volunteering, and helping others to increase the level of organized welfare. Organizational cynicism, however, reduces organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behavior, as well as job dissatisfaction and alienation (Abraham, 2000: 270). All these findings indicate that organizational cynicism is an attitude potentially having negative consequences both for employees as individuals and for the organization as a whole (Davis and Gardner, 2004: 442).

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Cynics harm their relationships because of their pessimism, and their skepticism about anything they learn may cause them to miss a good opportunity. However, at least in one point, cynicism can have positive consequences for both the individual and the organization. According to this, the cynics can express clearly that they are opposed to the organizational decision-makers' personal interests or their fraudulent behavior and thus act as the "voice of conscience" for the organization. As a result, organizational cynicism can not be said to be neither good nor bad for organizations (Dean, Brandes and Dharwadkar, 1998: 347). Despite organizational initiatives to motivate and keep employees active, cynicism continues to grow in organizations throughout the World (Öncer, 2009: 8). Today, researchers, organizational cynics, They argue that there are serious consequences for the organization. For organizational purposes organizational cynicism has often been associated with a series of negative consequences.

- Lack of organizational honesty
- Rumor that there is no organizational justice
- Rumor has it that unfair promotions have been made
- Criticizing organizational strategies and policies
- Decreased organizational commitment
- Increase in early retirement
- Decreased sense of belonging

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